

ON THE NUMERICAL MODELLING OF THE BEHAVIOUR OF MECHANICALLY JOINTED TIMBER BASED COMPOSITE CONNECTIONS

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Keywords: *FEM, screws, beam-to-solid coupling, timber-to-concrete, timber, composite structures, joints, Eurocode 5.*

1 Introduction

Timber-to-timber and timber-to-concrete structural joints are frequently achieved by metallic fasteners with cylindrical shanks, such as bolts, dowels, nails, screws, etc. Screws are very ancient and still widely used in practice because of their simplicity, ease, quickness of assembly, and offer many possibilities to obtain excellent ductility, which is crucial in seismic design [1, 2]. The deformation properties of these connections play a crucial role on the overall stability of the structure and on the distribution of internal forces.

In the design of screwed joints, the stiffness and the load carrying capacity values are key parameters that should be determined appropriately for a successful design. In the current standard practice, these parameters are generally assessed using the Eurocode 5 [3]. The load-carrying capacity of joints is estimated according to the timber embedment strength, the connection geometry and the yield moment of the fastener, while the stiffness, the so-called slip modulus, is estimated using the empirical formula suggested by the Eurocode 5 [3], depending on the fastener diameter and on the timber density. On the other hand, screwed connections have been extensively and comprehensively studied by several authors in the last decades. In recent years, the importance of screwed timber joints appeared clearly, because the high mechanical performance of modern joints compared to the traditional ones has increased their application. In fact, the availability on the market of self-tapping screws, characterized

by high withdrawal strength, allows obtaining connections endowed with high values of stiffness and load-carrying capacities [4].

Nowadays, the finite element method has increasingly and successfully been used as a powerful numerical tool for the design and the analysis of timber joints made with dowel-type fasteners. However, to date 3D FE models have mainly focused on bolted joints, with relatively large diameter, and very few 3D FE models for screws [5, 6] have been developed. In fact, the 3D detailed modeling of screws, using solid elements, would be very expensive in terms of computational time point of view. In fact, it requires the use of hundreds of thousands finite elements or even more to model screws, leading to unacceptable computational efforts [1].

For predicting the load-slip behavior of screwed joints, the authors developed recently a beam-to-solid approach (BTSA), which has been successfully applied to predict the load-slip curves of timber-to-timber [1] and timber-to-concrete connections [2], in the context of single plane push-out shear tests. In that approach, the screws were modeled using one dimensional beam elements, while the timber and concrete members were modeled in detail using solid elements. Since the degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) differ from the beam element to the solid element, the authors have modified the existing 2-node beam element, involving in a 4-node beam element with only translational d.o.f. [1, 2, 7], leading in fact to a full compatibility between the beam and the solid elements.

The aim of the present paper is to evaluate the appropriateness of the beam-to-solid approach, developed previously, in the context of inclined screws and especially its application to full-scale industrial examples. Of course, the formulation of the beam element is not the focus of this study and considered beyond the scope of the present paper. The reader is referred to papers [1, 2, 7] for a better reading on the formulation aspects.

The three main steps of the present work are the following: experimental, a brief description of the proposed beam-to-solid approach, numerical applications including single plane shear tests on both timber-to-timber and timber-to-concrete connections and finally a full-scale simply supported timber-to-concrete composite beam.

2 Experimental Program

Three kinds of examples have been considered in the experimental:

- timber-to-timber connection;
- timber-to-concrete connection;
- full-scale timber-to-concrete composite beam.

Before carrying out the mechanical tests, the mechanical properties of both timber and concrete materials have been, first, identified by appropriate experimental procedures.

2.1 Timber Characterization

The timber used in this study was spruce with average density of 420 kg/m^3 , at 12% moisture content. Compressive tests were performed axially and perpendicularly to the grain to determine the axial and transversal compressive strengths. The dimensions of the samples had a height of 20 mm and a cross section of $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$. The samples were loaded in compression in a standard Instron machine at the cross head speed of 2 mm/min . For each orientation, five samples were tested. The longitudinal modulus of elasticity E_0 was obtained from four-points bending tests, carried out according to EN 408 [8]. The other elasticity parameters were obtained according to EN 338 [9]. The average test results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Average test values for timber material

$\rho(\text{kg/m}^3)$	$E_0(\text{MPa})$	$f_{c,0}(\text{MPa})$	$f_{c,90}(\text{MPa})$
420	11000	36.5	2.6

2.2 Concrete Characterization

The concrete used to prepare the specimens was obtained by mixing aggregate, expanded clay cement with strength class of 42.5 and water. To assess the mechanical characteristics of the concrete, compression tests were conducted on three cylindrical normalized specimens of 16 cm diameter and 32 cm height. Table 2 summarizes the compressive test results. The modulus of elasticity E_{cm} , depending on the compressive strength (f_{cm}), was calculated by means the following relation, according to EN 1992-1-1:2005 [10]: $E_{cm}=22(f_{cm}/10)^{0.3}$. Based on the test results (Table 2), a mean value of characteristic strength of 30.1 MPa was obtained, at 28 days age, corresponding to the strength class of C25/30 according to EN 1992-1-1:2005 [10].

Table 2: Strength characteristics of concrete

Test	$\rho(\text{kg/m}^3)$	$F_{max}(\text{kN})$	$f_{cm}(\text{MPa})$	$E_{cm}(\text{GPa})$
1	2318	600	29.9	30.558
2	2313	625	31.1	30.920
3	2355	590	29.4	30.403
Average	2328	605	30.1	30.627

2.3 Push-Out Shear Tests

All push-out shear tests have been conducted according to the EN 26891:1991 Standard European Norm [11]. The parameters of the loading procedure were defined based on the maximum estimated load (F_{max}), which was obtained from preliminary test conducted until failure. The connection has been, first, loaded until 40% of F_{max} and the crosshead position held during 30s. After this stage, the connection has been unloaded until 10% of F_{max} and the crosshead position maintained again for 30s. Finally, the connection has been loaded until final failure.

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2.3.1 Timber-to-Timber

An experimental program which focuses on push-out shear tests of a single shear timber-to-timber connections, made of spruce (European whitewood), has been undertaken. Fig.1 gives the push-out shear test configuration and set-up. The specimens were composed by two lateral spruce wood members measuring 55 mm x 55 mm x 200 mm and central member measuring 55 mm x 70 mm x 200mm, interconnected using two round ordinary threaded screws of 5 mm of diameter and 120 mm of length, inserted at either an inclination angle of 90° or 45° with respect to the shear plane.

(a)

(b)

Fig.1: Push-out shear test specimens (dimensions in mm): (a) Specimen geometry, (b) Test set-up

Fig. 2 displays the experimental load-slip curves from three selected specimens, with screws inserted at 90°. Note that all the results achieved for the load-slip curves are quite homogeneous with very small Coefficient of Variation (CoV). It can be seen from these curves, that the non-linear behavior begins at a load level of 1.7kN corresponding approximately to a slip of 3.5 mm.

Fig. 2: Typical experimental load-slip curves from push-out shear tests with screws inserted at 90°.

2.3.2 Timber-to-Concrete

The configuration and the arrangement of tests conducted on timber-to-concrete specimens are shown in Fig. 3.

(a)

(b)

Fig.3: Push-out shear test (dimensions in mm): (a) Specimen geometry, (b) Test set-up.

The load-slip characteristics of timber-to-concrete specimens were also evaluated according to EN 26891:1991 [11], since at present there is not a standard shear test for timber-to-concrete connections [12, 13]. Three test arrangements are generally used, namely: push-out type with timber center and concrete sides, push-out type with concrete center and timber sides and pure shear type [13]. Based on the conclusions reported in [13], it has been decided to undertake push-out shear tests with timber center and concrete sides. All specimens were composed of timber center measuring 140 mm x 210 mm x 250 mm, interconnected using two round SFS-screws of 5 mm of diameter with threaded shank of 100 mm of length (one screw per side) to two concrete sides measuring 140 mm x 140 mm x 250 mm.

Fig. 4 displays the experimental load-slip curves from three specimens where it can be seen that the connections exhibit an initial slip part, followed by a linear behavior (hysteretic part) for relatively small slips and then the connection stiffness decreases as load increases and the global behavior over the complete loading range is nonlinear with a pronounced hardening. It can be also observed, from Fig. 4, that all specimens were failed after the maximum allowable slip level, in EN 26891, of 15 mm.

Fig.4: Experimental load-slip curves from push-out shear tests.

2.4 Full-Scale Timber-to-Concrete Composite Beam

In order to verify the appropriateness of the proposed BTSA on large size examples involving a large number of screws, four-points bending tests have been conducted on full-scale timber-to-concrete T-shaped composite beams (Figure 5), according to the EN 408 [8].

Fig.5: Four-point bending test arrangement (in mm)

In the construction of timber-to-concrete composite beams, spruce timber beams were connected to concrete slabs using SFS-screws VB 48-7.5-100, with a regular spacing of 80 mm.

Figure 6 illustrates the load-deflection curves from three beams tested until complete failure.

Fig.6: Experimental load-deflection curves.

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3 The Beam-To-Solid Approach (BTSA)

The main motivation of the BTSA is to develop a FE model that reduces the simulation efforts and able to work for large size industrial applications. In fact, as documented in the Introduction the 3D detailed modeling of screws, using solid elements, requires the use of hundreds of thousands small finite elements or even more to model screws, leading to unacceptable computational effort [1, 2]. This is particularly true in the case of large size industrial applications with a large number of screws. Although detailed modeling of screws using 3D solid elements can accurately predict stress and strain distributions within the timber (or concrete) members it would be very expensive in terms of computational time point of view.

In a typical screwed joint connection, the load transfer is achieved by relative slip of the connected members (timber or concrete). The internal forces acting on the screw are: tension (or compression), shearing and bending (Fig. 7).

Fig.7: Typical connection loaded laterally and forces acting on the screw: (a) timber-to-timber, (b) timber-to-concrete.

The shear force and bending are caused by bearing the screw against the timber (or concrete) surface, while the tensioning (or compression) is due to the axial withdrawal force, caused by the interaction conditions between the threaded screws hank and the timber as well as the screw-head embedment in the timber. The numerical approach presented here introduces the concept of assuming two different behaviors for the screw and the connected members. By neglecting the initial stresses caused by driving the screw into the timber, the basic idea is to use one-dimensional beam element to predict the behavior of the steel screws and detailed 3D solid elements to predict the behavior of the timber (or concrete) members (Fig. 7).

This is referred to as beam-to-solid coupling. In a general beam-to-solid coupling, it is necessary to deal with the stiffness contribution of the solid element to the rotation of the section of the beam element [13], since the d.o.f. differ from the beam element to the solid element. However, this leads to a clamping condition which is obviously not fulfilled for screws in timber. Therefore, the basic idea is to use one-dimensional beam element (Figs. 8a and 8b) to model the steel screws and detailed 3D elements to model both the timber and the concrete members.

Fig.8: The global flowchart of the beam-to-solid approach [2].

In this study, the authors use a special 4-node beam element with only translational d.o.f., which has been obtained by the modification of the existing 2-node beam element, with translational and rotational d.o.f. [1, 2, 7]. That beam element has been developed, especially to deal with beam-to-solid coupling related to modeling problem that arise when screws in timber are considered.

Of course, the use of one-dimensional beam element to model screws leads naturally to a simplified modeling of some local effects like the interaction between the timber and the threaded shank of the screw that should not affect noticeably the global behavior but can play an important role on the stress distribution within the timber.

4 Numerical Simulations

The ABAQUS finite element code was used to investigate the behavior of the jointed connected members (timber and concrete) with screws. Since the connection geometries admit two plans of symmetry, only one quarter was modeled for each application example (Fig. 9). 3D finite element model was assumed and eight-node solid elements have been used for the discretization of both the timber and concrete members (Fig. 9). Orthotropic anisotropic elasto-plastic material model [14-15] has been assumed for the timber behavior. The concrete was assumed as isotropic and elasto-plastic material, while the screws have been assumed as isotropic elasto-plastic material and modeled using 4-node one-dimensional beam element. The material properties of the screws are: $E= 210 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu= 0.3$, $\sigma_y= 400 \text{ MPa}$. Coupling constraints have been applied to the common nodes between the screws, timber and concrete members. The contact formulation, between timber/concrete interfaces, is based on the master-slave contact approach supported in ABAQUS finite element code. The Coulomb friction model has been used with a frictional ratio $\mu = 0.2$ and the interaction between the contact interfaces has been formulated using the finite sliding approach, which allows separation of the interfaces during sliding.

Fig.9: Typical finite element mesh of the timber-to-concrete connection studied (one quarter).

4.1 Results From Timber-to-Timber Connection

By neglecting the initial slips of the experimental curves, the comparison between the experimentally and numerically predicted load-slip behaviors for all specimens are illustrated in Fig. 10. Also, it can be observed that the numerical approach predicts well the full non-linear behaviors of joints, whatever the angle of inclination of the screws. The slight differences which can be observed in the post-elastic regions can be attributed to the progressive bearing damage in the timber members, which has not been taken into account in the present finite element approach.

Fig. 11 illustrates the distribution of the equivalent stresses within the timber members at a slip level of 20 mm. It can be observed that the stresses are concentrated around the screw locations. The stresses were higher along the screw depths than elsewhere on the timber members. This indicated the regions of embedding stresses. Note that at this stage of the study, the accuracy regarding the distribution of stresses within the assembled members (timber and concrete) has not yet been verified qualitatively.

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(a)

(b)

Fig.10: Comparison between the numerically and experimentally predicted load-slip curves:
(a) screws at 90°, (b) screws at 45°.

Fig.11: Equivalent stress distributions within the timber members at 20 mm slip level.

4.2 Results From Timber-to-Concrete Connection

Fig.12 shows the predicted load-slip curves for the studied timber-to-concrete composite connections. A fairly good agreement is found between numerically predicted results and those obtained from the experimental results. It is worth noting that the nonlinear load-slip relationship is accurately predicted until a slip level of 20 mm. Beyond this slip level, the accuracy is not satisfying because the progressive damage caused in both timber and concrete has not been considered in the present model. Based on Fig. 12, it can be concluded that the present approach can well predict the slip modulus of connections and the load-carrying capacity up to failure initiation.

Fig.12: Comparison between the numerically and experimentally predicted load-slip curves.

Fig. 13 displays the equivalent stress distributions in the connection at 100% slip level corresponds to a slip of 20 mm. It can be observed that the stresses are concentrated around the screw locations. Also, visible is the depth involved by these stress concentrations. The stresses were higher along the screw depths in the concrete side than elsewhere on the connection and the stress increases as the slip level increases. Again, more verification is needed to validate the appropriateness of the stress distributions within the assembled members, since the modeling of the interaction between the screws and the assembled members has been simplified.

Fig.13: Equivalent stress distributions within the assembled members at 20 mm slip level.

4.3 Results From Timber-to-Concrete Composite Beam

The numerically predicted load–deflection curve is plotted for FE modeling against the corresponding experimental results, which are shown in Figure 14. A fairly good correlation can be observed.

Fig.14: Comparison between the numerically and experimentally predicted load-deflection curves.

Figure 15 shows the stress distribution where it can be seen that the stresses are higher in the screw location regions.

Fig.15: Equivalent stress distribution at deflection level of 80 mm.

4.4 Parametric Study

The load-slip curve of joints is closely related to some parameters like the screw diameter, the friction between the timber members in contact, etc. In order to understand the sensitivity of the developed numerical approach to some parameters, the influence of the screw diameter and the friction coefficient on the load slip curve have been computed. The friction coefficient varies between $\mu = 0$ and $\mu = 0.5$ and the screw diameter varies between $d = 3 \text{ mm}$ and $d = 8 \text{ mm}$.

Fig.16 Influence of the friction coefficient on the load-slip curve.

Fig. 16 displays the influence of the friction coefficient between the timber members in contact on the load-slip behavior. It can be seen that the

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frictional conditions do not have significant effect on the linear elastic range of the global behavior but, it slightly affect the nonlinear range of the load-slip behavior.

The Fig. 17 shows the influence of the screw diameter and the results show a clear and significant effect on the yield load.

Fig.17 Influence of the screw diameter on the load-slip curve.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, a simplified way, called beam-to-solid approach (BTSA), to predict the load-slip behavior of screwed joints is proposed and validated against experimental results. In the BTSA, the screws are modeled using a special one-dimensional beam element, with only translational degrees of freedom, while the assembled members are modeled in detail using solid elements. Thus, the interaction between screws and timber, i.e: the contact between the threaded shank of the screw and the timber as well as the crushing zone in the timber beneath the screw were not modeled in detail, but represented using multi-point coupling constraints. At our best knowledge, this neglected local effect does not affect the global behavior of joints but can play an important role on the stress distributions. The obtained results demonstrate clearly that the proposed approach can adequately predict the load-slip curve of joints, since it shows close results to reality.

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